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Research Article

WHITENING STRIPS ARE THEY SAFE AND EFFECTIVE?

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Abstract:

Background: Nowadays, the market of esthetic world proposes a lot of at home bleaching options; one of them is whitening strips. At home whitening strips were found to be effective in teeth whitening without tissue irritation and/or teeth sensitivity. When comparing in-office and at-home bleaching in efficiency and safety, there were no significant difference in color shade between in-office and at-home treatment. It has become more and more difficult and challenge for dentists to determine the effectiveness of various tooth-whitening systems, while keeping patients' safety paramount as manufacturers continue to provide new products that purport to be superior to others currently on the market.

Aim: To evaluate the effectiveness and safety of whitening stripes compared to in-office bleaching system.

Objectives: 1. To demonstrate the amount of demineralization caused by whitening strips. 2. To compare the whitening effect and surface demineralization of whitening strips to a well-established in-office bleaching.

Material and method: Twenty extracted human anterior teeth; free from caries, non-carious lesions, and/or defects were used in the present study. The collected teeth were cleaned from gross debris and stored in normal saline at room temperature till use. Each crown of the stored teeth was sectioned vertically into two equal halves from incisal edge to CEJ with both halves kept attached to the root. Crowns incomplete sectioning created two groups: group (A) was treated with 3D crest whitening strips LUXE professional effect while; group (B) was treated with Philips zoom in-office bleaching gel. DIAGNOdent was used to measure the amount of surface demineralization for each half at the center while; VITA Easyshade Advance 4.0 was used to determine the shade for each half at the center.

Results: there was a significant increase in minerals loss (demineralization) for In-office bleaching system (Zoom) when compared to surface demineralization caused by over-the-counter whitening strips (Crest) at (P-value = 0.05). There was an improvement in enamel shade after application of both bleaching methods, But According to Wilcoxon test this change was not significant at (P-value= 0.05). Over-the-counter whitening strips (Crest) showed a significant color change at (P-value =0.015), compared to In-office bleaching system (Zoom).

Conclusions: 1. Samples bleached with the over the counter whitening strips showed significantly less surface demineralization than those bleached with in-office bleaching system. 2. Change in shade was significant in samples treated with the whitening strips compared to those bleached in-office bleaching gel.

Key words: whitening strips, demineralization, color change.

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difference in color change between pre and post whitening treatment with mild teeth sensitivity and gingival irritation immediately after treatment, but there were no significant difference in color shade between in-office and at-home treatment [4].

It has become more and more difficult and challenge for dentists to determine the effectiveness of various tooth-whitening systems, while keeping patients' safety paramount as manufacturers continue to provide new products that purport to be superior to others currently on the market [7].

Many studies about effectiveness and safety of whitening strips have been published. However, few researches compared the effectiveness and safety of whitening strips to in-office bleaching system. Therefore, the aim of this in vitro study was to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of whitening strips in compare to in-office bleaching system, and demonstrate the amount of demineralization caused by whitening strips.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design

Two bleaching systems were used in the present investigation: *Philips zoom in-office bleaching gel* and *3D crest whiting strips LUXE professional effect*. Twenty extracted human anterior teeth; free from caries, non-carious lesions, and/or defects were used. The collected teeth were cleaned from gross debris and stored in normal saline at room temperature till use, then each crown of the stored teeth was sectioned vertically into two equal halves from incisal edge to cement-enamel junction with both halves kept attached to the root.(Figure1) Crowns incomplete sectioning created two groups: group (A) was treated with whitening strips while group (B) was treated with an in-office professional bleaching.

Group (A): Over the counter whitening strips

Bleaching strips were peeled and applied on enamel slabs for 30 minutes once daily for twenty days. (Figure 2)

Group (B): In-office bleaching procedure.

Zoom bleaching gel was applied on enamel slabs for 45 minutes and reapplication of fresh gel is done every 15 minutes. Freshly applied gel was activated by light of zoom machine at high intensity level. (Figure 3)

Testing procedures

DIAGNOdent was used to measure the amount of surface demineralization for each half at the center. while; VITA Easyshade Advance 4.0 was used to

INTRODUCTION:

Esthetic dentistry has received increased attention in recent years, especially due to the fact that people are more concerned about the esthetic appearance of their smile [1]. This fact has made the whitening of discolored teeth (bleaching) to become a popular procedure. Dental bleaching is oxidation procedure of substance that cause stain by the use of chemical agents such as hydrogen peroxide (HP) to get brighter colors of teeth.

The result of bleaching differs from person to person depending on the type and amount of stain, type of bleaching protocol used, type and concentration of active ingredient, contact time of the bleaching agent, and degree of commitment of the patient to post bleaching procedure instructions.

Nowadays, the market of esthetic world proposes a lot of at home bleaching options; one of them is whitening strips, which are considered the easiest and cheapest way to whitening teeth. Many patients come to dental clinic and ask about whitening strips if their effect is similar to in-office bleaching systems and whether they are safe or not. The most common adverse effects reported for at-home bleaching systems are tooth sensitivity and gingival irritation, which disappear when the bleaching treatment is stopped or an agent like potassium nitrate or sodium fluoride is applied [2]. At home whitening strips were found to be effective in teeth whitening without tissue irritation and/or teeth sensitivity [3].

Also, after comparing two at home products with different administering methods but same (HP) concentration, the teeth color changed with mild soft tissue sensitivity with no significant difference in color change between both products [4]. The investigation of tissue irritation, tooth sensitivity and color change after treatment with at-home novel over-the-counter bleaching tray system, there were significant change in teeth color with no tooth sensitivity and tissue irritation [5].

In-office dental bleaching has been practiced for more than 100 years and has some advantages over at-home bleaching which allows dentist to control bleaching treatment; avoid soft tissue irritation and enhancement of the shade of teeth in one clinical appointment.

Investigation of the effectiveness and safety of different in-office bleaching systems revealed that there were color improvement but with tooth sensitivity after the application of the bleaching gels [6]. When comparing in-office and at-home bleaching in efficiency and safety, there was a significant

after the bleaching procedures.

Figure (1): vertical sectioning of the teeth

Figure (3): In-office bleaching procedure

The mean values for surface demineralization of over-the-counter whitening strips (Crest) before and after its application were (0.30 ± 0.571) and (1.10 ± 1.714) respectively with no significant difference between them. While, for In-office bleaching system (Zoom) the mean values were (0.20 ± 0.523) and (2.10 ± 2.972) with a significant difference between them at $(P\text{-value} = 0.05)$, according to Wilcoxon test. Also, there was a significant increase in minerals loss (demineralization) for In-office bleaching system (Zoom) when compared to surface demineralization caused by over-the-counter whitening strips (Crest) at $(P\text{-value} = 0.05)$. (Table 1 & Figure 5).

Delta E (ΔE) represents the measurement of visual color change. The increase in delta E value means more color change. There was an improvement in enamel shade after application of both bleaching methods, But According to Wilcoxon test this change was not significant at $(P\text{-value} = 0.05)$. The mean value of delta E for over-the-counter whitening strips (Crest) was (13.130 ± 2.2200) which

determine the shade for each half at the center. (Figure 4). All measurements were taken before and

Figure (2): Over the counter whitening strips applied on enamel slabs

Figure (4): VITA Easysshade Advance 4.0

Statistical Analysis Data were collected and statistically evaluated. The appropriate statistical test was Wilcoxon test to compare between over the counter whitening strips (3D crest whitening strips LUXE professional effect) and in-office professionally applied bleaching system (Philips zoom in-office bleaching gel) in surface demineralization and change in color (delta E).

Wilcoxon test is a non-parametric test alternative to t-test for matched, related, repeated samples. It was selected because the samples were: 1-Matched sample (The teeth were sectioned to obtain two enamel slabs from each crown.) 2-Repeated measurement sample (Each sample was examined prior and after bleaching procedures.).

Forty enamel slabs of maxillary incisors were used in this study. Twenty slabs received over the counter whitening strips (3D crest whitening strips LUXE professional effect 14% HP). The rest twenty slabs received in-office professionally applied bleaching system (Philips zoom in-office bleaching gel 35% PH).

(Zoom), which was (10.915 ± 4.0714) . (Table 2, Figure 6).

showed a significant color change according to Wilcoxon test at (P-value =0.015), compared to the mean value of delta E for In-office bleaching system

Table (1): Descriptive statistical analysis of the surface demineralization of the investigated groups:

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	±Std. Deviation	P-value
Surface demineralization before (strips)	20	0	2	0.30	±0.571	>0.05
Surface demineralization after (strips)	20	0	6	1.10	±1.714	
Surface demineralization before (zoom)	20	0	2	0.20	±0.523	
Surface demineralization after (zoom)	20	0	9	2.10	±2.972	

Figure 5: Bar chart representing difference between surface demineralization after both bleaching protocols.

Table (2): Descriptive statistical analysis of the change in shade (ΔE) of the investigated groups:

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	\pm Std. Deviation	P-value
Delta E for (strips)	20	10.1	17.4	13.130	\pm 2.2200	0.015
Delta E for (zoom)	20	3.9	21.1	10.915	\pm 4.0714	

Figure 6: Bar chart representing change in shade after both bleaching protocols.

The improvement in colour can be explained by three phenomena: first, the hydrogen peroxide leads to dehydration and oxidation of hard dental tissue and make change in colour [10,11]. Secondly, rough surface (demineralized surface) lead to more reflection of light than smooth surface and make the object brighter, finally, opalescent effect at small structures -due to surface demineralization- leads to increase in back scattered short wavelength that is reflected as bluish-white; [12,13].

In the present investigation, *VITA Easy shade Advance 4.0* was used to calculate the change in color: Delta E (ΔE) which is the measurement of visual color change representing the difference

DISCUSSION:

There is a general believe among the general population and anecdotal evidence among dentist practitioners that in-office bleaching is superior to at-home bleaching. Some manufacturers claim that high concentration hydrogen peroxide bleaching agents are superior and faster compared to the low concentration at-home products [8].

In this in-vitro study there was an improvement of teeth shade after application of both bleaching methods which indicates the effectiveness of both bleaching methods regardless of concentration of hydrogen peroxide. [3, 4, 6, 9]

and morphology, depending on the bleaching protocol; [25, 26].

In the present research, over-the-counter whitening strips showed non-significant loss of enamel surface after its application, which was in disagreement with Worschech et al., 2006 who found that Over-the-counter bleaching agent significantly increased the enamel surface loss and roughness [27]. In general, the bleaching effect changes the enamel surface characteristics, and under experimental studies, bleaching can cause progression of tooth demineralization; [28, 29, 30].

RECOMMENDATION:

In this study we recommend in-office bleaching over at-home whitening strips which was better controlled by dentist and with less soft tissue irritation.

LIMITATION:

The limitation of this study is post treatment evolution of small sample size after short period of time that lead to low statistical power and less reliability of result.

Future study should be evaluated the color change at least after month of bleaching in large sample size.

CONCLUSIONS:

1. Samples bleached with the over the counter whitening strips shows significantly less surface demineralization than those bleached with the professionally applied in-office bleaching.
2. Change in shade was significant in samples treated with the whitening strips compared to those bleached with professionally applied in-office bleaching gel.

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between color of two objectives; [14]. When value of ΔE is more than 3.3 the human eyes can detect colour difference; [15].

In this study the mean value of ΔE obtained immediately after application of the whitening strips was ($\Delta E=13.13$) and for the in-office zoom bleaching system was ($\Delta E=10.92$). Over the counter whitening strips showed more colour change than zoom bleaching this result was in agreement with *Zekonis et al., 2003* who concluded that the at-home bleaching had more whitening effect than in-office bleaching and he recommended that patient would need longer time of in-office bleaching to get results similar to at home bleaching [16]. This was also in agreement with *Auschill et al., 2005* who stated that "teeth bleached with at-home bleaching had brighter color when compared with teeth bleached with the in-office bleaching" [17].

In the other hand there were some studies concluded that there was no significant color change between at-home and in-office bleaching; [6,18,19].

In the present study the degree of surface demineralization was measured before and after application of each bleaching protocol where the mean values for surface demineralization for samples treated with over-the-counter whitening strips (Crest) before and after its application were (0.30 ± 0.571) and (1.10 ± 1.714) respectively with no significant difference between them. While, for In-office bleaching system (Zoom) the mean values were (0.20 ± 0.523) and (2.10 ± 2.972) with a significant difference between them at ($P\text{-value} = 0.05$).

It is essential to emphasize that dental enamel is the most mineralized tissue of the human body, with approximately 89% by volume of inorganic elements, 2% organic components and 9% water; [20]. Disruption of the enamel organic matrix caused by hydrogen peroxide results in loss of the crystalline material sketched out of this matrix, leaving zones of erosion intercalated with areas of intact enamel, resulting in a rough demineralized surface; [21, 22]. This could be an explanation for the results obtained by this investigation.

Moreover, these results were in agreement with *Rodrigues et al., 2009* who suggested that hydrogen peroxide was able to dissolve the enamel organic matrix regardless its concentration [23]. While, *Sa Y et al., 2013* explained the surface minerals loss after application of different bleaching agents by the drop in PH from seven to five [24]. However, several studies demonstrated that the effects of bleaching agents on dental enamel might vary from insignificant up to deep alterations on its structure

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